

Disruptive electrical propulsion - power processing unit

Horizon Europe project DEEP PPU

Novelty Zero Current Detection Sensor for MHz frequency range

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AUTHOR: FRAZA

For the purposes of the EU co-funded project DEEP PPU, consortium partner FRAZA has developed an advanced Zero Current Detection Sensor (ZCD sensor) having an extremely low latency, volume and losses.

Developmental process of the Zero Current Detection Sensor

The most suitable yet simple concept of zero current detection utilizes a small transformer driven into saturation. This concept hides significant potential of achieving very low losses, a good noise immunity, high accuracy and fast responsiveness. The concept operates by detecting the moment of the magnetic core falling out of the saturation at the moment of the current changing the polarity. The change in flux of the magnetic core induces voltage in a detection coil which is then reflected in a form of a voltage pulse.

Co-funded by
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The challenges of such a design are primarily low losses and low latency. Facing these challenges FRAZA developed three prototypes. The first prototype was built to prove the concept. The latency was still large (~100 ns) and strongly dependent on the current's first derivative. The second prototype improved the latency to approximately 10 ns and reduced the latency dependence. This prototype has an additional in-built housing for an effective heat dissipation. Finally, the third prototype reduced the losses by 90% and introduces a cost-effective serial production.

Figure 1: Current sensor developmental stages; 1st prototype (left), 2nd prototype (middle) and 3rd prototype (right)

Properties of the ZCD Sensor

Outstandingly good properties are achieved by the third prototype of the ZCD sensor developed by FRAZA. The dimensions of the sensor are 6 mm x 6 mm x 1 mm. It achieves latency between 7 ns and 15 ns while simultaneously having losses below 100 mW at 1 MHz and 50 App.

Figure 2: Measurement of ZCD sensor operation with a red marked section (left), detailed enlargement of the red marked section demonstrating latency of 7.7 ns (right)

About project

The DEEP-PPU consortium will develop a disruptive Power Processing Unit for medium and high-power GIT. The project is a natural continuation of GIESEPP-MP, where a first step has been taken to develop a power supply for the screen grid and integrate it within the current PPU design for ArianeGroup RIT-2X thruster. The activity is focused on the improvement and optimization of the power electronics as one of the major cost drivers of an electric propulsion system, in particular for gridded ion technology.

Project consortium

DEEP-PPU team is composed of 6 organisations. Each of the partners is responsible for a specific work package or task within the project. Most of the partners have worked together before. The consortium is led by Airbus Crisa (Spain).

Airbus Crisa

Airbus Crisa
Project coordinator & PPU
www.crisa.es

Polytechnic University of Madrid Centro de Electrónica Industrial
Responsible for Radiofrequency Generator electronics
www.cei.upm.es

AIRBUS

Airbus DS
Responsible for / definition of space specific requirements
www.airbus.com

AXON CABLE
Responsible for interconnection of systems / Manufacturer for space harness assemblies
www.axon-cable.com

WIT Berry
Responsible for communication and dissemination activities
www.witberry.eu

Fraza
Responsible for expertise in magnetics design
www.fraza.si

Competitive advantages proposed by DEEP-PPU

DEEP PPU team's proposed solutions stands out with significant mass and cost reduction compared to the existing solutions on the market. It aims to strengthen the EU's space sector competitiveness in the international market and secure the autonomy of supply for critical technologies and equipment.

50%
Cost reduction

30%
Mass and volume reduction

The integration of the RFG unit within the PPU

